

Innovative concepts and technologies for ECOLOGically sustainable NUTRIent management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air

Newsletter – Issue 3

October 2024

WELCOME

Welcome to the third edition of the **Econutri** Newsletter! Within these pages, you will find news and updates on our activities. We invite you to subscribe and explore our website! Follow us on social media and learn more about the world of **Econutri**.

[Econutri website](#)

Celebrating the second year of ECONUTRI

**3rd General Assembly in Skierniewice, Poland
28–31 October 2024**

The **Econutri** consortium gathered in Skierniewice, Poland for a four-day General Assembly to celebrate the project's second year. It was hosted by the [National Institute of Horticultural Research \(InHort\)](#). With 60 in-person participants, the meeting featured insightful site visits, progress updates, and engaging discussions on nutrient recycling, emission reduction, and sustainability. Stakeholders from Poland and China shared their visions and interest in **Econutri's** outcomes while the China-EU collaboration was reinforced through joint research efforts.

A big thank you to **InHort** for their warm hospitality, treating us to wonderful dinners, lively Polish music, and traditional dances that made our time in Skierniewice even more memorable!

📖 Read the full article on our [website](#).

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Main accomplishments

During the last six months all partners have been working towards **Econutri's** main goals and the following highlights per WP, are showcasing the rapid progress and collaborative achievements across all work packages.

WP1 – Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation (CETRI, SPI)

In the last six months, WP1 updated the ECONUTRI website (including a Stakeholder Forum), met Year 2 dissemination targets, and refined partner exploitation plans. Social-media engagement grew, and EU-China collaboration continued successfully.

WP2 – Innovative Technologies for Organic Matrices (UNITO, NIBIO, HAAS)

Task 2.1 is nearly complete: partners optimized manure storage and composting protocols to minimize nutrient losses. Task 2.2 (nutrient calibration and precision dosing) is halfway done, with "FarmsApp" integration underway. Task 2.3 pilots are now defined at multiple sites (e.g., biogas + compost, slurry separation, nanobiochar), and these demonstrations will ramp up in early 2025.

WP3 – Innovative Cropping Technologies (WUR, UAL, UTH, NAU, CAU, Stanley)

Field-crop and vegetable-crop trials showed improved nitrogen-use efficiency via real-time sensors and UAV mapping. Soilless (hydroponic) pilots reduced nitrate leaching, and greenhouse studies with biostimulants (PGPR, biochar) recorded a 20 % reduction in N₂O emissions. Partners are preparing joint hackathons and summer schools to integrate these innovations into decision-support tools.

WP4 – Nature-Based Technologies for GHG & NH₃ Reduction (EV ILVO, ATB, CAU)

WP4's barn and storage trials moved ahead: ATB and ILVO tested manure-removal frequencies and microbial additives, while ARI and UTAD initiated biochar and biochar + acidification experiments. Field trials on variable manure dosing and biostimulants began, and ATB's sensor network for real-time gas monitoring expanded to include methane. The first datasets will be ready by February 2025, with workshops on sensor calibration planned.

WP5 – Environmental Impacts & Socioeconomic Assessment (IGZ, ESSRG)

The draft LCA model was completed for one hydroponic innovation, with D5.1 on schedule. ESSRG's eDelphi Round 1 collected stakeholder views on nature-based solution adoption, and Rounds 2 & 3 are launching early

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2025. A policy brief will summarize recommendations.

WP6 – Data Management & system-level analysis (JHI, NIBIO)

JHI and NIBIO consolidated metadata (77 Meta Forms) and SOPs; the systematic review manuscript is in draft. SPI/ESSRG ran the first eDelphi and will issue four policy briefs by Summer 2025. Partners are aligning LCA and NbS criteria through joint WP5/6 meetings to ensure data accuracy and policy relevance.

Econutri in the spotlight

[Seminar](#): The transition from NIBIO's ending project Mafigold to the new project **Econutri**, 7 May 2024

[Webinar](#) dedicated in presenting the Virtual Lysimeter, an innovative tool developed by WUR to help greenhouse growers optimize irrigation and fertilization. 4 June 2024

[Brandenburg Land Parties Event](#) by ATB on 8 June 2024

[Seminar by ARI](#) for Cypriot Stakeholders on June 13, 2024 at the village of Sotira.

[Il Campus della Sostenibilità](#), by UNITO, in Grugliasco, Italy. It was 3-hour public event dedicated to environmental awareness and sustainable innovation. 15 June, 2024

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[AgritechDay2024](#) by ILVO,
18 June 2024, Belgium

[AgEng2024 Conference](#), in Athens,
Greece, where UTH presented
their findings on a cascade
hydroponic system, 1-4 July 2024.

[Mid-term meeting](#) in Heihe City, China
of the Chinese partners
hosted by CAU and HAAS,
20 July 2024

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[ISHS International Symposium](#), titled "[1 International Symposium on Protected Cultivation, Nettings and Screens for Mild Climates](#)", hosted by
AUA, in Athens, Greece, 23-26 September 2024

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Growing Impact: EU–China Journey

The EU–China partnership within **Econutri** has continued to deepen and flourish from May to October 2024. **Econutri** coordinator Dimitrios Savvas visited Chinese partners **HAAFS** and **NAU**. Furthermore, AUA and CAU visited the active stakeholder **Rui Feng Ecological Group**, while HAAFS colleagues traveled to **UAL** (Spain) and **WUR** (Netherlands) to share insights on sustainable fertigation. In turn, Chinese researchers visited **NIBIO's** facilities in Norway, and INHORT represented **Econutri** at a **major conference** in China and **visited HAAFS**.

A major **milestone** during this period was the successful co-organization of the **first Joint Stakeholder Conference**, held at AUA in Athens on September 26–27, 2024, in collaboration with the research projects **Econutri**, **Trans4num**, and **PestNu**. The event brought together European and Chinese partners along with key stakeholders to work side by side on real-world agricultural solutions, focusing on sustainable nutrient and water management in protected cultivation systems.

These exchanges deepened scientific ties, unified research directions, and laid the groundwork for nature-based solutions that reduce nutrient losses, optimize resource use, and strengthen agricultural resilience across both regions. Further details on all these events are available in the “**News**” section of the **Econutri** website covering updates from May to October 2024.

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Future Events

1. [Field Day at the demonstration site of ATB-Potsdam](#) “Digitalization and remote sensing in crop production”, on 6 November 2024
2. Online Workshop “Innovative Solutions for Sustainable Agriculture”, will be organized by UTAD, UNITO, NIBIO and HAAS, on 13 December 2024.
3. [Annual BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conference](#) at the Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences, Bucharest, Romania, on 9-10 April 2025.
4. EU and Chinese Partners are planning to organize online workshops and additionally Econutri Chinese partners and stakeholders plan to visit EU sites.

Econutri Partners

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